

Synthesis of Steroidal and Terpenoidal Extranucleo Thiazolidinones

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3-Oxo-5 β -cholan-24-oic-acid (1a), 3-oxo-lanost-8,24-diene (2a) and 3-oxo-olean-12-ene (3a) on reaction with hydrazine hydrate in alcoholic solution gave the respective 3-hydrazones (1b, 2b and 3b). Subsequent reaction of these 3-hydrazones with ammonium thiocyanate in benzene solution afforded 3-thiosemicarbazone derivatives (1c, 2c and 3c) which undergo cyclisation with chloroacetic acid in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate to yield 3-[4'-oxo-1',3'-thiazolidin-2'-ylidene-hydrazino]-5 β -cholan-24-oic acid (1d), 3-[4'-oxo-1',3'-thiazolidin-2'-ylidene-hydrazino]lanost-8,24-diene (2d) and 3-[4'-oxo-1',3'-thiazolidin-2'-ylidene-hydrazino] olean-12-ene (3d), respectively.

In view of the useful biological activities¹ of thiazolidinones, we have undertaken the synthesis of steroidal and terpenoidal thiazolidinones. In present investigation thiazolidinone ring was built up on C-3 of bile acid, lithocholic acid (1), tetracyclic triterpene, lanosterol (2) and pentacyclic triterpene, β -amyrin² (3).

3-Oxo-5 β -cholan-24-oic acid (1a), 3-oxo-lanost-8,24-diene (2a) and 3-oxo-olean-12-ene (3a) were reacted with hydrazine hydrate in alcoholic solution to obtain the corresponding hydrazones (1b, 2b, 3b),

- (1) 3 α -OH, 3 β -H
(2, 3) 3 β -OH, 3 α -H
(1a, 2a, 3a) O
(1b, 2b, 3b) N-NH₂
(1c, 2c, 3c) N-NH-CS-NH₂

which when refluxed with ammonium thiocyanate in benzene solution gave the respective thiosemicarbazones (1c, 2c, 3c).

The cyclisation of (1c, 2c, 3c) with chloroacetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate and acetic acid furnished 3-[4'-oxo-1',3'-thiazolidin-2'-ylidene-hydrazino]-5 β -cholan-24-oic acid (1d), 3-[4'-oxo-1',3'-thiazolidin-2'-ylidene-hydrazino]lanost-8,24-diene (2d), 3-[4'-oxo-1',3'-thiazolidin-2'-ylidene-hydrazino]olean-12-ene (3d), respectively. Spectral data of the compounds are presented in Table 1. The ¹³C nmr data were assigned by comparison with the spectra of 5 β -cholan-24-oic acid derivatives³, lanostan-3 β -ol derivatives⁴, triterpene diol derivatives⁵ and thiazolidinone derivatives⁶. The alternate structures (1e, 2e, 3e) are precluded on the basis of ¹³C nmr data as they are expected to show the signal for CH₂ of thiazolidinones at δ 85–90 τ .

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a JEOL FX-90 Q FT instrument with TMS as internal standard and ¹³C nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a JEOL JNN FX-100 (25.00 Mz) spectrometer (temp. 25 $^{\circ}$) using TMS as internal standard. Petroleum ether refers to the fraction of b.p. 60–80 $^{\circ}$. Analytical, physical and spectral data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

Hydrazones (1b, 2b, 3b): A mixture of the ketone (1a, 2a, 3a; 2.5 g), hydrazine hydrochloride (0.1 g) and freshly distilled hydrazine hydrate (2 ml) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The excess of solvent was then distilled off and the residual solution was poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (1.98 g); ν_{\max} 3 300, 3 100 (NH₂) and 1 480 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

Thiosemicarbazones (1c, 2c, 3c): To the hydrazone (1b, 2b, 3b; 2 g) in benzene (100 ml) was added ammonium thiocyanate (2 g) and the mixture was

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula
1b	78	270–72	C ₂₄ H ₄₁ N ₂ O ₂
2b	78	174–76	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ N ₂
3b	80	106–07	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ N ₂
1c	82	218–20	C ₂₅ H ₄₂ N ₃ O ₂ S
2c	84	182–84	C ₃₁ H ₅₁ N ₃ S
3c	82	250–52	C ₃₁ H ₅₁ N ₃ S
1d	58	170–72	C ₂₇ H ₄₂ N ₃ O ₃ S
2d	55	122–24	C ₃₃ H ₅₁ N ₃ OS
3d	57	82–84	C ₃₃ H ₅₁ N ₃ OS

1d ν_{\max} 3 250 (NH), 1 715 (C=O), 1 460 (C=N), 1 240 cm⁻¹ (C–S–C); pmr δ 8.2 (1H, s, NH; D₂O exchangeable), 4.82 (2H, s, CH₂ of thiazolidinone), 1.01 (3H, d, *J* 6 Hz, C₂₁-H₃), 0.91 (3H, s, C₁₉-H₃), 0.73 (3H, s, C₁₈-H₃); ¹³C nmr δ 216.2 (C=O), 174.6 (COOH), 157.2 (C=N), 68.5 (CH₂ of thiazolidinone), 12.2 (C-18), 23.2 (C-19), 18.1 (C-21), 31.4 (C-23); 2d ν_{\max} 3 240 (NH), 1 710 (C=O), 1 450 (C=N), 1 250 cm⁻¹ (C–S–C); pmr δ 8.1 (1H, s, NH; D₂O exchangeable), 4.75 (2H, s, CH₂ of thiazolidinone), 5.12 (1H, t, C=CH), 0.73 (3H, s, C₁₈-H₃), 1.15 (3H, s, C₁₉-H₃), 1.0 (3H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz, C₂₁-H₃), 1.05 (3H, s, C₂₉-H₃), 0.94 (3H, s, C₂₉-H₃), 0.87 (3H, s, C₃₀-H₃); ¹³C nmr δ 217.4 (C=O), 157.6 (C=N), 68.2 (CH₂ of thiazolidinone), 134.6 (C-8), 134.2 (C-9), 15.8 (C-18), 19.2 (C-19), 18.7 (C-21), 125.1 (C-24), 130.9 (C-25), 28.1 (C-28), 16.5 (C-29), 24.32 (C-30); 3d ν_{\max} 3 280 (NH), 1 710 (C=O), 1 470 (C=N); 1 250 cm⁻¹ (C–S–C); pmr δ 8.2 (1H, s, NH; D₂O exchangeable), 4.80 (CH₂ of thiazolidinone), 5.18 (1H, t, C=CH), 1.05 (3H, s, C₂₉-H₃), 1.02 (3H, s, C₂₄-H₃), 1.10 (6H, s, C₁₈, C₂₆-H₃), 1.17 (3H, s, C₂₇-H₃), 0.82 (3H, s, C₂₈-H₃), 0.90 (6H, s, C₂₉, C₃₀-H₃); ¹³C nmr δ 216.8 (C=O), 158.4 (C=N), 69.1 (CH₂ of thiazolidinone), 121.2 (C-12), 142.6 (C-13), 22.8 (C-23), 16.7 (C-24), 15.6 (C-25), 25.9 (C-26), 30.1 (C-27), 29.9 (C-28), 33.2 (C-29), 21.3 (C-30).

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

refluxed on a water-bath for 3 h. The excess benzene was then distilled off and the concentrated solution on cooling gave a pale yellow solid which was recrystallised from methanol to yield the product (1.85 g).

Thiazolidinones (1d, 2d, 3d): A mixture of the thiosemicarbazone (1c, 2c, 3c; 1.5 g) and chloroacetic acid (0.5 g) was refluxed in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate (0.5 g) and acetic acid (50 ml)

for 6–8 h. The excess solvent was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the concentrated solution was poured into ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with sodium bicarbonate (5%), water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of solvent furnished a semisolid which was chromatographed over silica gel (60 g; 70–230 mesh). Elution with and petroleum ether-ether (10:1) gave a solid which was recrystallised from ethanol.

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